

Exploring Special Needs Through Neuroscience

A Psychology + Neuroscience Report by Diya Kannan

Introduction

Growing up, I've seen and experienced what it means to live with and care for someone with special needs. My dad and I went through a lot together, trying to understand how to support my special needs brother and make sense of the challenges he and my disabled mom faced. My brother's perspective and my mom's approach to life inspired me to explore the science behind it. Going more into detail about how the brain works and in people who think and learn

differently. When I was a kid, thousands of questions would come to me about every small action my mom or brother would do. Maybe the result of those actions seemed different to them? Or is their brain just wired in a completely different way than mine in how they see the world? As I grew older these questions became more interesting to me like; what causes someone to behave the way they do - is it because of emotion, choice or something deeper than what we usually think about? All of these thoughts are what led me to research how the brain processes information, makes decisions, and shapes behavior. Instead of just wondering, I started looking for real answers in science, especially in psychology and neuroscience. Conditions like autism, ADHD, and dyslexia helped me understand how complex and unique every brain is doing research, and how science can help explain that. Special needs and people with disabilities are often judged or misunderstood in society; understanding them better can lead to more kindness, better support, and a world that works for everyone, not just for people who fit into what's considered normal. Through this report I want to understand and spread awareness on how psychology and neuroscience explain the behaviour, challenges and strengths of individuals with special needs, and hopefully you do too.

Understanding Special Needs

When we hear the word “special needs” or “disabled”, a lot of us tend to think about the physical and speaking challenges which leads to a majority of us thinking that they're less capable, even when that's not true. But, the word special needs actually has so many meanings and conditions from learning difficulties to disorders. A lot of these conditions aren't always visible to us which can make them hard to comprehend. For example, if you take someone with ADHD they might not always sit quietly or focus, but that doesn't imply that they're not smart it just means they

have their own ways of learning and expressing their abilities. Another problem with our society is that people always focus on what a person with a disability or special needs can't do instead of what they can do very well. I've experienced this firsthand as my brother does well in social areas and likes meeting new people, but sometimes finds learning more challenging. All of these experiences helped me understand and be patient when I'm around people with special needs. We often take an idea and make that the goal or normal way of life but special needs remind us that there is not only one way of being successful or smart. Learning more about all these conditions and ways of living, helps us understand all the different people around us and makes the world a more interesting place to live in.

The Brain and Behaviour

After reading the article ("Brain Development: Neuro-Behavioral Perspectives in Developmental Disabilities"), the brain starts developing before birth and through childhood and teenage years. Any trouble that happens throughout these stages can be due to genetic, infection or environmental issues and can lead to disabilities happening while developing. Many of these disabilities aren't random, they are linked to changes in how the brain forms and connects. For example, in kids with autism, things that change in the cerebral cortex will affect how they speak, which makes communication harder. In ADHD, the prefrontal cortex which controls attention span tends to develop differently, which leads to trouble focusing or hyperactivity. In cerebral palsy, the damage happens early to areas like the motor cortex which leads to challenges in movement. The article also states that mental and physical health are connected so the way the brain grows impacts emotion, replies, and even how the body feels pain. All of these examples

show how each person's encounter with a disability can be very different, depending on which brain systems were affected while developing.

Neuroscience Behind Learning Differences

Neuroscience can help explain why people with special needs have different ways of learning. For example, in dyslexia, the brain's language areas are the ones that handle word recognition which don't connect in the same way as in a typical brain. This is what makes spelling and reading harder even though the intelligence isn't affected. In ADHD, the brain connections involving the prefrontal cortex develop differently, which impacts attention, control and the ability to plan tasks. Autism also shows brain patterns which are unique, with the differences in connectivity between the parts that handle communication, sensory stuff and emotion. These differences are the main struggle when it comes to things like school or processing information fast. Aside from this, neuroscience also shows that the brain is flexible, it's a concept called 'neuroplasticity'. With good support, like visual help and extra time, students can explore these ways of learning, helping them make progress. This takes away the stereotype from what they can't do, and rather shows how their brains work differently, which is why these learning methods are so important.

Personal Connection

My connection to this topic is deeply personal. Growing up with a brother who has special needs shaped the way I see people, the way I learn, and the world as a whole. I didn't just observe his

challenges, I saw his strengths, his personality, and the way he experienced life differently from me. Being there for him taught me patience, empathy, and the importance of trying to understand someone before making assumptions. It also opened my eyes to how society often misunderstands people with disabilities, focusing more on their struggles than on the abilities they bring. My experiences at home motivated me to learn more about how the brain works and why people think and behave differently. Instead of seeing “special needs” as a limitation, I began to see it as a different way of interacting with the world. This personal journey is what pushed me toward studying psychology and neuroscience, not just to answer the questions I had as a kid, but to help build more understanding and support for people like my brother.

Support and Education

Support and education has a role in helping people with special needs succeed. Schools often provide Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) or other learning programs, which are designed to match a student’s strengths and challenges. For example, a student with dyslexia may get more time on reading tasks, audiobooks, or reading programs that use both sight and sound. Children with ADHD benefit from routines, breaks, or tools like planners and timers to stay on track. In autism, support often includes therapies to build communication and social skills, along with classroom adjustments to reduce the sensory part. Teachers, parents, and friends also make a big difference. When they understand that learning differences are caused by how the brain works, not by effort or ability, they can provide encouragement. More than school, early intervention programs and community resources can give families tools to help children build

their own confidence and independence. The overall goal of support and education is not to fix differences, but to provide fair opportunities so that every student can reach their potential.

Conclusion

Understanding special needs using psychology and neuroscience helps us see that differences in thinking, learning, and behaving are not flaws, they are natural changes in how the brain develops and functions. Research shows that conditions like autism, ADHD, and dyslexia are in unique brain patterns, not a lack of intelligence or potential. When society focuses on what individuals can do instead of what they struggle with, we make space for inclusion and growth. My personal experiences with my brother taught me how important patience, empathy, and knowledge are. With the right support, whether at home, in school, or in the community, people with special needs can live in their own ways. By understanding the science behind these differences and recognizing the capability within each person, we move closer to a world where everyone's abilities are valued. This report isn't just about learning the facts, it's about spreading kindness, awareness, and a deeper appreciation for the many ways different people experience the world.

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